

Detection and characterization of endogenous avian leukosis virus obtained from contaminated avian vaccines

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Abstract

In this study the reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT- PCR) and the enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) were utilized for screening of different live avian viral vaccines to detect biocontamination with avian leukosis virus (ALV). By using ELISA test, the group specific antigen of avian leukosis virus was detected in three batches of Marek's disease virus (MDV) vaccines as well as in one batch of avian encephalomyelitis virus (AEV) vaccine. To identify the subgroup of the contaminant ALV, contaminated samples were tested by RT – PCR using sets of primers specific to the envelope (*env*) gene of avian leukosis virus. Virus subgroup was determined by running simultaneously 6 RT- PCR reactions. Results of RT- PCR revealed detection of subgroup E specific product in all four ELISA – positive vaccine batches. No PCR products were detected with primers designed for detection of exogenous virus subgroups A, B, C, D, or J. Trials for isolation of ALV from contaminated vaccines were failed after inoculation and incubation in chicken embryo fibroblast cell cultures for 21 days, indicating inability of the contaminant ALV to replicate in inoculated cultures. Detection sensitivity of RT – PCR was 1000 – fold higher than that of ELISA. Results indicate that both ELISA and RT-PCR are reliable assays for detection of vaccine contamination with ALV, although ELISA is still lacking the ability to differentiate between different ALV subgroups. These disadvantages of ELISA could be overcome by using RT-PCR which is proved as a rapid, specific and sensitive technique for both the detection and characterization of ALV.

Key words: Avian leukosis virus, extraneous viruses, RT-PCR, contaminated vaccines.

Introduction

Avian leukosis virus (ALV) is the type species of the genus *Alpharetrovirus* of the family Retroviridae. Members of this family of avian viruses are

characterized by possession of an enzyme reverse transcriptase, which directs the synthesis of the proviral DNA form of the RNA virus that forms part of the retroviral life cycle and from which the family name

is derived (Nair and Fadly 2013). Infection with ALVs is prevalent in most chicken flocks causing serious economic losses since infected chickens may exhibit reduced growth rates, decreased egg production, and produce eggs of reduced size and quality (Gavora et al., 1982). In addition, ALV causes tumors and sporadic deaths in sexually mature chickens (Fadly and Nair, 2008). At least six subgroups of avian leukosis viruses, A, B, C, D, E, and J have been identified in chickens based on differences in the envelope (*env*) glycoprotein. The exogenous oncogenic ALV subgroups A, B, C, D, and J are horizontally and vertically transmitted in chickens. Subgroup E ALVs are endogenous non – oncogenic viruses that are transmitted in a noninfectious form from one generation of chickens to the next in a Mendelian fashion along with the host genes (Pham et al., 1999). The vertical route of transmission is the most important epizootiologically because it affords a means of maintaining the infection from one generation to the next (Payne and Nair 2012). Since most vaccines are propagated and produced in chicken embryo – derived substrates, so if such embryos are derived from infected hens, the derived substrates will represent the most common route for entrance of adventitious pathogens into vaccines. Over

the past few decades, an increase in the incidence of vaccine contamination with retroviruses was recorded. Too many studies have been reported on detection of avian leukosis virus and/or reverse transcriptase as contaminants in avian and human vaccines, as well as in substrates used for vaccine production (Barbosa and Cheng, 2008, Boni, et al., 1996, Burmester, et al., 1956, Churchill 1968, Dougherty and Harris, 1966, Hanafusa, et al., 1970, Hussain, et al., 2003, Johnson, and Heneine 2001, Moemen, et al., 2010, Oshel, et al., 1970, Payne, et al., 1966, Richman, et al., 1972, Robertson, et al., 1997, Zavala, and Cheng 2006, Zhao, et al., 2014). During 2014, the Central Laboratory for Evaluation of Veterinary Biologics (CLEVB) had received different batches of avian live viral vaccines to be tested for quality. For detection of extraneous virus contamination, all batches were screened by different routine tests, including *in – vivo* and *in – vitro* assays. Among these assays, ELISA was the test that had been conducted for detection of ALV as vaccine contaminant. Evidence of contamination with ALV was recorded in some vaccine batches. Since the currently available commercial ELISA kits are entirely designed to detect P27, a group specific antigen shared by all ALV subgroups, so

this test is not enough for differentiation between exogenous and endogenous ALVs. Moreover, ELISA test is unable to differentiate between different ALV subgroups (Garcia, et al., 2003, Smith, et al., 1998). Therefore, an alternative technique should be searched to overcome these disadvantages of ELISA. Reverse transcriptase – polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) is considered a sensitive, convenient, and reliable assay for detection and differentiation of all ALV subgroups by using group specific primer sets (Garcia, et al., 2003, Hauptli, et al., 1997, Kim, and Brown 2004, Pham, et al., 1999, Zhou, et al., 2011). The aim of this study was assessing RT-PCR as an alternative technique to ELISA in screening of vaccines for detection and identification of ALV contamination.

Materials and methods

Vaccines: Different batches of live avian viral vaccines were received for detection of extraneous virus contamination. All batches were screened by *in – vitro* and /or *in – vivo* assays for detection of various viral contaminants. In this study, exactly 216 batches were tested for detection of biocontamination with avian leukosis virus.

ELISA for detection of ALV antigen:

The ELISA for detection of ALV antigen in target vaccine samples was conducted in

two phases; the first is virus propagation in chicken embryo fibroblast (CEF) cultures and the second is assay for ALV presence by testing of inoculated CEF cultures for detection of P27 by ELISA. In some trials, ELISA was conducted directly on vaccine samples without tissue culture inoculation (direct assay). Propagation of ALV – if present – was performed in 216 vaccine batches in sequential manner in several trials. The test was conducted in CEF cell cultures prepared according to standard procedures (Schat, and Sellers 2008). From 9 – 11 days – old chicken embryos derived from SPF chicken flocks (Kom Osheem, Fayoum, Egypt). Virus propagation was performed as described (Fadly, et al., 2008) Briefly, CEF cells were suspended in tissue culture medium at a concentration of 2.5×10^5 / ml and then dispensed in 6 – well tissue culture plates. When cultures reached confluence, test samples were inoculated into drained cultures at the rate of 0.1 ml (10 doses) per well. Cultures were incubated at 37° C for 30 min then fresh medium was added. Uninoculated cultures were served as negative control. All cultures were incubated at 37°C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere for 7 – 9 days. At the end of incubation period, 80 µl of 5% Tween 80 was added per culture and all cultures were subjected to three cycles of freezing and

thawing to release cell associated virus antigen. IDEXX ELISA kit batch no. DKO53 was used for detection of p27 antigen as described by kit manufacturer.

RT- PCR Assay for ALV: RT- PCR assay was conducted for detection of ALV as vaccine contaminant as follow:

- *Nucleic acid Extraction:* Each vaccine sample was rehydrated in 5 ml nuclease free water, and 200 µl samples were used for extraction of viral nucleic acid using *GENEAID* viral nucleic acid extraction kit II (batch no. FC06804 – P). Nuclease free water was served as negative control. The procedures for viral nucleic acid extraction were as described by the manufacturer.
- *ALV RT-PCR:* RT-PCR for detection of ALV was conducted by using *QIAGEN*® *one step RT-PCR* kit (lot no. A157027098). Procedures of RT –

PCR were as described by the manufacturer. The RT-PCR assay included the following reagents in the reaction tube: 10 µl of 5 X RT- PCR buffers, 2.0 µl of dNTP mix, 3.0 µl of each primer (BIOMATIK) with final concentration of 0.6 µM, 2 µl enzyme mix, 10 µl of RNA template, and nuclease free water was added to reach 50 µl reaction volume. Data of ALV Primers used are shown in table (1). Nuclease free water was used as negative control. ALV positive control was received from reference strain bank, CLEVB. Samples were amplified in *TECHEN Plus* thermo cycler. The cycling conditions are shown in table (2). PCR products were analyzed by electrophoresis on 1.5 % agarose with ethidium bromide (0.5 µg/ml), and gels were visualized using transilluminator (CS Cleaver).

Table (1) Oligonucleotide primes used in ALV RT-PCR.

ALV subgroup	Primer	Sequence (5'-3')	Size (bp)	Reference
A	PA10-F	GGC TTC AGG CCA AAA GGG GT	232	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PA20-R	GTG CAT TGC CAC AGC GGT ACT G		
B	PB1-F	GGC TTT ACC CCA TAC GAT AG	259	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PB2-R	ACA CAT CCT GAC AGA TGG ACC A		
C	PC1-F	TAT TTC GCC CCA AGG GCC AC	238	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PC2-R	CCA CGT CTC CAC AGC GGT AAG T		
D	PD1-F	GGC TTC ACC CCA TAC GGC AG	258	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PD2-R	CCA TAC GTC CTC ACA GAT AGAATA		
E	PE1-F	GGC TTC GCC CCA CAC TCC AA	265	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PE2-R	GCA CAT CTC CAC AGG TGT AAA T		

J	ALV- J1-F	GGA TGA GGT GAC TAA GAA AG	245	Ottiger, (2010).
	ALV- J2-R	CGA ACC AAA GGT AAC ACA CG		
A, B, C, D, E	PU1-F	CTR CAR CTG YTA GGY TCC CAG T	229/2 46	Pham, et al., (1999)
	PU2-R	GYC AYC ACT GTC GCC TRT CCG		

*R = A/G, Y = T/C

Table (2): Cycling conditions for one step RT-PCR

Step	Temperature	Time
Reverse transcription	50°C	30 min
Initial PCR activation	95°C	15 min
30 cycles of 3-steps		
Denaturation	94°C	40 sec
Annealing	53°C	40 sec
Extension	72°C	1 min
Final extension	72°C	10 min

Investigation on the origin of ALV in

positive sample: Since both RT – PCR and

ELISA assays are unable to determine whether the contaminant virus is infectious or noninfectious virus, so another assay should be conducted to investigate the origin of p27 antigen in contaminated vaccines. The most reliable and standard assay for this purpose is the biological assay or virus isolation in cell cultures. Trials for isolation of avian leukosis virus from the contaminated vaccine samples were attempted. In such trials, vaccine samples were rehydrated in 10 ml MEM, then 0.1 ml was inoculated on drained confluent CEF cultures and incubated for 30 min at 37 ° C for adsorption then maintenance medium was added and cultures were maintained at 37 ° C for 21 days incubation period which included two passages, at 7th and 14th days of inoculation. Samples of cells and culture

fluid were collected at the end of each passage and stored at – 80 ° c. At the end of incubation period, ELISA test was conducted on harvests of the three passages for detection of p27 antigen as described above.

Sensitivity of ELISA and RT-PCR for detection of ALV:

The contaminated vaccines were tested by both assays; direct ELISA and RT- PCR to compare between the detection limit for each assay. For this purpose, each vaccine sample was rehydrated in 10 ml buffer and then diluted in ten – fold series from 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁵. All dilutions were simultaneously tested by direct ELISA and RT-PCR to determine the least detection limit that could be detected with each assay.

Assay for detection of avian leukosis virus in CEF cultures:

Twelve batches of chicken embryo fibroblast (CEF) cultures were screened by RT- PCR for detection

of avian leukosis virus as an adventitious pathogen. Cultures were prepared as described by standard procedures (**Schat and Sellers 2008**), and maintained for at least 7 days, and then samples of culture fluid were saved and used for extraction and amplification of ALV by RT-PCR using 6 pairs of primer sets designed for detection of all ALV subgroups.

Results

ELISA for detection of ALV in vaccines:

The presence or absence of P27 antigen in test samples was determined as described by the kit manufacturer by relating the mean optical density value of the sample to positive control mean. The relative level of P27 in the sample was determined by calculating the sample to positive (S/P) ratio. If this ratio is less than or equal to 0.2, the sample was considered negative. If the S/P ratio is greater than 0.2, the sample was considered positive for P27 antigen. Result of ELISA revealed the detection of p27 antigen in 4 out of 216 vaccine batches. Of these four contaminated vaccine batches, 3 are Marek's disease vaccine (Rispens strain) and one is avian encephalomyelitis virus (AEV) vaccine. The obtained S/P ratios for contaminated Rispens were 0.36, 0.28, and 0.31, while for avian encephalomyelitis virus vaccine was 0.56 (table 3). Negative

result was obtained in 212 batches of various live viral vaccines with an S/P ratio range of 0.06 – 0.16. On the other hand, the range of S/P ratio for uninoculated cell cultures (negative test control) was 0.08 – 0.14, and that of positive test control ranged from 0.48 to 0.56.

Detection of ALV by RT-PCR: Avian encephalomyelitis virus vaccine and the three MDV vaccines batches that have been tested positive by ELISA were tested by RT-PCR for identification and differentiation of the contaminating ALV. In the first trial, all samples were tested with one primer, PU1/PU2. This primer set is designed for detection of all ALV subgroups A – E, but not subgroup J. Results revealed detection of a product of approximately 240 base pairs in all four batches. This result is in accordance with that obtained by ELISA, and confirmed the contamination of these vaccines with one or more of ALV subgroups from A – E.

Characterization of ALV: To identify the subgroup to which the contaminant ALV is related, the contaminated vaccines were tested against each of 6 primers designed for ALV subgroups, A, B, C, D, E, and J. A product specific for subgroup E avian leukosis virus of approximately 265 bp was detected in 4 out of 4 tested vaccines by using PE1, PE2 primer set. No product

was detected by using any of the five primer sets designed to detect each of A, B, C, D, and J subgroups (figure 1). PU1/PU2 and PE1/PE2 primers. As shown in figure 2, a product of approximately 240 bp was amplified with primer PU1/ PU2 (lane 2), and a product of 265 bp was amplified with primer PE1/PE2 (lane 3). The primer set PE1/PE2 produced a distinct smear in the agarose gel, and the intensity of color and zones are clearer than that for PU1/PU2 primers.

Investigation on the origin of P27 antigen in contaminated vaccines: To investigate whether the origin of p27 antigen in the contaminated vaccine samples is due to replication – competent or defective ALV, trials for virus isolation in CEF cultures were attempted. Results in table 4 showed positive results only in the first passage, with mean S/P ratio of 0.31, 0.27, 0.33 for MDV vaccines, and 0.42 in AEV vaccine. However, values of S/P ratio did not significantly increased in 2 successive passages, as S/P ratios for MDV vaccines were 0.14, 0.16, 0.16, and 0.18 for AEV vaccine in the 2nd passage, while in the 3rd passages they were 0.15, 0.12, 0.14 for MDV vaccine, and 0.14 for AEV vaccine. These results indicate that there is no evidence of virus replication in the second and third passages (table 4).

On the other hand, samples that have been tested directly from contaminated MDV and from AEV vaccines without cell culture propagation (direct assay) were strong positive, with S/P ratio of 0.47, 0.38, 0.45 for MDV vaccines, while in AEV vaccine it was 0.96.

Sensitivity of ELISA and RT-PCR:

Serial ten –fold dilutions (from 10^{-1} to 10^{-5}) were prepared from contaminated vaccines and were simultaneously tested by ELISA as well as RT- PCR to compare the sensitivity or detection limit for both tests. By using ELISA, P27 antigen could be detected up to 10^{-1} dilution, but not in higher dilutions. On the other hand, by using PE1/PE2 primers, RT-PCR enabled detection of ALV in contaminated vaccines up to 10^{-4} dilution (table 5).

Detection of endogenous avian leukosis virus in CEF cultures:

Twelve batches of CEF cultures were screened by RT- PCR for detection of ALV contamination using 6 pairs of primer sets specific for detection of all ALV subgroups A – E and J. Results showed amplification of a product of 265 base pairs specific for subgroup E avian leukosis virus in all tested cell batches (12/12) indicating presence of endogenous avian leukosis virus (fig.3).

Table (3) Results of ELISA test for detection of P27 antigen in different live avian vaccines.

Test samples	ELISA results	
	S/P ratio	Interpretation *
MD vaccine serial no. 126/014	0.36	Positive
MD vaccine serial no. 218/014	0.28	Positive
MD vaccine serial no. 355/014	0.31	positive
AE vaccine serial no. 94/014	0.56	Positive
Different vaccine batches (212)	Range = 0.06 – 0.16	Negative all
Uninoculated CEF cultures	Range =0.08 – 0.14	Negative all
Positive ALV control	Range = 0.48 – 0.56	Positive

* S/P ratio less than or equal to 0.2 is considered negative result, S/P ratio more than 0.2 is considered positive.

*MD: Marek's disease; AE: Avian Encephalomyelitis.

Fig.1. RT-PCR for detection of ALV in contaminated AEV vaccine using group

RT-PCR for detection of ALV in contaminated AEV vaccine using group – specific ALVs primers. Lane 1: subgroup A primer. Lane2: subgroup B primer. Lane3: subgroup C primer. Lane 4: subgroup D primer. Lane 5: subgroup E primer. Lane 6: subgroup J primer. Lane7: Nuclease free water. M: Molecular weight DNA marker.

Figure 2: RT- PCR for detection of ALV in contaminated MDV vaccine

ALV in contaminated MDV vaccine batch no. 355/014 using PU1/PU2 and PE1/PE2 primers. Lane 1: Nuclease free water tested with PU1/PU2 primer. Lane 2: MDV vaccine tested with PU1/PU2 primer. Lane 3: MDV vaccine tested with PE1/PE2 primer. Lane 4: Nuclease free water tested with PE1/PE2 primer. M: DNA molecular weight marker.

Table (4) Result of ELISA for detection of ALV antigen in contaminated vaccine samples with and without propagation in CEF cultures.

Test samples	Mean S/P ratio at X passages*			Direct assay
	1 st passage	2 nd passage	3 rd passage	
MDV vaccine batch no. 126/014	0.31 positive	0.14 Negative	0.15 negative	0.47 positive
MDV vaccine batch no. 218/014	0.27 -positive	0.16 Negative	0.12 Negative	0.38 Positive
MDV vaccine batch no. 355/014	0.33 positive	0.16 Negative	0.14 Negative	0.45 Positive
AEV vaccine batch no. 94/014	0.42- positive	0.18 Negative	0.14 negative	0.96 positive

* S/P ratio of less than or equal to 0.2 is negative. S/P ratio of more than 0.2 is positive.

Table (5) Results of direct ELISA and RT – PCR for detection of ALV in serial 10 – fold dilutions of contaminated AEV vaccine.

Method	Samples of AEV vaccine at x dilutions					
	Original stock	10 ⁻¹	10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁵
ELISA	Pos.	Pos.	Neg.	Neg.	Neg.	Neg.
RT-PCR	Pos.	Pos.	Pos.	Pos.	Pos.	Neg.

Figure3: RT- PCR for detection of avian leukosis virus in CEF culture

RT- PCR for detection of avian leukosis virus in CEF cultures using 6 primer sets designed for different ALV subgroups A, B, C, D, E, and J (lanes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6; respectively. Lane 7: negative control. M: molecular weight DNA marker.

Discussion

By using ELISA test, the group specific antigen of avian leukosis virus was detected as vaccine contaminant in three batches of Marek’s disease vaccines and in one batch of avian encephalomyelitis vaccine. Although ELISA has been reported as a highly specific and sensitive assay for detection of ALV (Smith, et al., 1977), it cannot differentiate between ALV subgroups, as well as it cannot determine whether the positive result is due to the presence of replication – competent exogenous or defective endogenous virus. This is because all entirely current ELISA kits are designed for detection of P27, which is a capsid protein that shared by all avian leukosis virus groups (Fadly, and Nair, 2008). To investigate the origin of p27 in contaminated vaccines, biological assay

revealed positive result only in the first passage, while the second and third passages were negative, which indicates inability of the contaminant ALV to replicate in CEF cultures. Failure of replication may be explained by either the contaminating virus is a replication – defective incomplete virus belonging to subgroup E endogenous ALVs, or the inoculated CEF cultures are resistant to ALVs infection or both possibilities. However, the later possibility seems less probable than the previous one in view of the fact that CEF cultures were prepared from chicken embryos obtained from SPF flocks that have not genetically selected, i.e.it have considered susceptible for infection with all ALV subgroups. The first suggestion is more likely, and it was confirmed by the result obtained by RT – PCR. Contamination of avian vaccines

with endogenous avian leukosis virus is well documented in different types of vaccines as well as in vaccine substrates (Tsang, et al., 1999, Weissmahr, et al., (1997). The non-infectiousness of endogenous ALV viruses is likely due to a minor deficiency or change in the envelope structure. When the endogenous virus is incomplete (defective), genes present may be expressed phenotypically but infectious virus is not produced. This is because the absence of the complete set of genes needed for infectious virion production (Johnson and Heneine, 2001, Robertson, et al., 1997). The presence of endogenous virus genes in this manner is responsible for positive reactions in the ELISA and COFAL tests. (Nair and Fadly (2013) this may be explaining the discrepancy that had been obtained in our results in values of S/P ratio in-between the three passages. Since the contaminant ALV is endogenous virus, it is unable to propagate in CEF cultures and it will be considered as an antigen, and so it will be directly affected with the dilution rate, and the result will be proportionally related with its concentration in test sample. In the first passage, 0.1 ml of the contaminated vaccine was used as inoculum; this means that the contaminant ALV was diluted at the rate of 1: 30 (0.1 ml inoculum / 3.0 ml medium). It seems

that this rate of dilution is still detectable by ELISA. In the second passage, the inoculum was greatly diluted to reach about 1: 900 (0.1 ml of the 1st passage / 3.0 ml medium), and so on in the 3rd passage. These limits of ALV antigen concentrations may be undetectable by ELISA. This explanation is augmented by results of ELISA conducted on cell culture – propagated as well as on non-propagated vaccine preparation. The obtained S/P ratio was at its maximum level in non-propagated stock vaccine preparation, while this level decreased dramatically to undetectable limits especially in the second and third passages. Results of RT-PCR confirmed results obtained by ELISA. By using PU1/PU2 primer a specific product of approximately 240 base pairs was detected, indicating contamination with one or more of avian leukosis virus subgroups. To determine the contaminating virus subgroup, samples of the contaminated vaccines were tested using primer set designed to detect one type of the six ALV subgroups at a time. The only positive result was obtained with PE1/PE2 primer that was capable to identify subgroup E only, confirming contamination of test vaccines with endogenous avian leukosis virus, the same result that had been obtained by ELISA. Interestingly, results of figure (3) showed

that a PCR product of approximately 265 bp, specific for ALV subgroup E was detected in some batches of CEF cultures, indicating its contamination with endogenous avian leukosis virus. It should be noted that all these CEF batches were tested negative for P27 by using ELISA, the case which raises a critical question about the discrepancy of results between ELISA and RT-PCR especially in testing non inoculated CEF cultures which were used as negative test control. Presence of endogenous viruses in normal chicken cell is well documented by several workers. (Crittenden, 1991). stated that the normal chicken genome contains several classes of families of avian retroviruses – like elements that are transmitted genetically and are termed endogenous viruses. These include the endogenous viral (*ev*) loci, endogenous avian virus (EAV), avian retrotransposon from chicken genome (ART-CH), and chicken repeat elements (CR1). The genetic sequences of the *ev* loci are related in subgroup E ALVs and are present as either complete or defective genomes almost in all normal chickens (Crittenden, 1981; Payne, and Nair, 2012; Smith, 1987) reported that at least 29 *ev* loci have been identified. The discrepancy between ELISA and RT-PCR results in detection of endogenous ALV in CEF cultures may be explained by the fact

that the sensitivity of RT-PCR is more efficient than that of ELISA, and thus RT-PCR could detect the very low levels of the endogenous virus (*ev*) present in CEF cultures which could not be detected by ELISA. Results in table (5) strengthen this suggestion, as the comparison between sensitivity of ELISA and RT-PCR in detection of ALV in contaminated vaccine sample revealed that RT-PCR was more sensitive and it could detect ALV in contaminated vaccine up to 10^{-4} , while ELISA could detect ALV antigen in 10^{-1} dilution, but not less. This means that RT-PCR is 1000 times more sensitive than ELISA. Failure of ELISA to detect *gs* antigen in some samples with low levels of endogenous virus has been reported by some authors (Fadly, et al., 1981; Smith, et al., 1977). who reported that ELISA cannot detect ALV group specific antigen in culture fluids contain less than 8×10^4 infectious units of ALV. (Clark and Dougherty, 1980) stated that ELISA could not detect less than 0.3 ng/ml of AMV protein in culture fluid or approximately 8 pg input protein per test well. In conclusion; both ELISA and RT-PCR are reliable assays for the detection of vaccine contamination with ALV, although ELISA is still considered less sensitive than RT-PCR and lack the ability of differentiation between different ALV subgroups. These

disadvantages of ELISA could be overcome by using RT-PCR which is proved as a rapid, specific and sensitive technique for both the detection and characterization of ALV in contaminated vaccines and will be useful in vaccine quality control laboratories for monitoring of vaccine contamination with ALV.

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References

1 - Barbosa, G Zavala, and S Cheng, 2008. Molecular characterization of three recombinant isolates of avian leukosis virus obtained from contaminated Marek's disease vaccine. *Avian Dis.*, 52: 245-252.
2 - Boni J, J Stalder, F Reigel and J Schupbach, 1996. Detection of reverse transcriptase activity in live attenuated vaccines. *Clin. Diagn. Virol.*, 5: 43-55.
3 - Burmester B R, C H Cunningham, G C Cottral, R E Belding and R F Gentry, 1956. The transmission of visceral lymphomatosis with (live virus) Newcastle disease vaccine. *Am. J. Vet. Res.*, 17: 283-289.
4 - Churchill A E, 1968. Studies on the serological and interfering properties of avian leukosis virus isolates from field outbreaks of disease and from three vaccines. *Res. Vet. Sci.* 9: 68-75.
5 - Clark D and R Dougherty, 1980. Detection of avian oncovirus group - specific antigens by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. *J. Gen. Virol.*, 47: 283- 291.

6 - Crittenden L B, 1981. Exogenous and endogenous leukosis virus genes - a review. *Avian Pathology*, 10: 101- 112.
7 - Crittenden L B, 1991. Retroviral elements in the genome of the chickens. Implication for poultry genetics and breeding. *Crit. Rev. Poultry Biol.*, 3: 73-109.
8 - Dougherty R M and R J C Harris, 1966. Contaminant viruses in two live virus vaccines produced in chicken cells. *J. Hyg. Camb.*, 64: 1-7.
9 - Fadly A M and Nair V, 2008. Leukosis /sarcoma group. In: *Diseases of poultry*. 12th edition, pp 512 - 588.
10 - Fadly, A. M., W. Okazaki, E. J. Smith, and L. B. Crittenden (1981). Relative efficiency of test procedures to detect lymphoid leukosis virus infection. *Poultry science*, 60:2037-2044.
11 - Fadly, A.M., Witter, R.L., and Hunt, H.D. (2008). *Oncornaviruses Leukosis/Sarcomas and Reticuloendotheliosis*. In: *A laboratory manual for the isolation, identification and characterization of avian pathogens*. 5th edition, pp 164-172.
12 - Garcia., J. EL-Attrache, S.M. Riblet, V.R. Lunge, A.S. Fonseca, p. Villegas, and N. Ikuta (2003). Development and application of reverse transcriptase nested polymerase chain reaction test for the detection of exogenous avian leukosis virus. *Av Dis.*, 47:41-53.
13 - Gavora S., Spencer, J.L., Chambers. J.R. (1982). Performance of meat - type chickens test - positive and negative for lymphoid leukosis virus infection. *Avian Pathol.*, 11, 29 - 38.
14 - Hanafusa, T., T. Miyamoto, and H. Hanafusa (1970). A type of chick embryo cell that fail to support formation of infectious RSV. *Virology*, 40: 55 - 64.
15 - Hauptli, D., L. Bruchner, and H. P. Ottiger. (1997). Use of reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction for detection of vaccine contamination by avian leukosis virus. *J Virol Methods.*, 66: 71-81.

- 16 - Hussain, A.I, J.A. Johnson, M. Da Silva Freire, and W. Heneine (2003). Identification and characterization of avian retroviruses in chicken embryo- derived yellow fever vaccines: Investigation of transmission to vaccine recipients. *J Virol.*, 77:1105-1111.
- 17 - Johnson, J.A., and W. Heneine (2001). Characterization of endogenous avian leukosis viruses in chicken embryonic fibroblast substrates used in production of measles and mumps vaccines. *J Virol.*, 75: 3605-3612.
- 18 - Kim, Y., and T.P. Brown. (2004). Development of quantitative competitive-reverse transcriptase- polymerase chain reaction for detection and quantitation of avian leukosis virus subgroup J. *J Vet Diagns Invest.*, 16: 191- 196.
- 19- Moemen, A.M., Y. A. Tolba, A. I. Awad., and E. S. Moustafa (2010). Contamination rate of avian leukosis viruses among commercial Marek's disease vaccines in Assiut, Egypt market using reverse transcriptase- polymerase chain reaction. *Veterinary World*, 3(1):08-12.
- 20 - Nair, V., and A. M. Fadly (2013). Leukosis/Sarcoma group. In: *Diseases of Poultry*. 13th edition chapter 15.
- 21 - Oshel, D.D., D. R. Wenger, T. A. Koski (1970). Monitoring poultry vaccines for biocontamination with lymphoid leukosis virus. 107th Annual AVMA Meeting, Las Vegas, Nevada, June 23-26, 150-157.
- 22 - Ottiger, H.P. (2010). Development, standardization and assessment of PCR systems for purity testing of avian viral vaccines. *Biologicals.*, 38:381-388.
- 23 - Payne, L.N., P. M. Biggs., and R. C. Chubb (1966). Contamination of egg adapted canine distemper vaccine by avian leukosis virus. *Vet Rec.*, 78:45-49.
- 24 - Payne, L.N., and V. Nair (2012). The long view: 40 years of avian leukosis research. *Av Pathol.*, 41:1-9.
- 25 - Pham, T.D., J. L. Spencer, V. L. Traina-Dorge, D.A, Mullin, R. F. Garry, and E. S. Johnson (1999). Detection of exogenous and endogenous avian leukosis virus in commercial chicken eggs using reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction assay. *Av Pathol.* 28: 382-389.
- 26 - Richman, A.V., C.G. Auliso, W. G. Jahnes, and N.M. Tauraso (1972). Avian leukosis antibody response in individuals given chicken embryo derived vaccines. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.* 139:235-237.
- 27 - Robertson, j. S., C. Nicolson, A. Riley, M. Bently, G. Dunn, T. Corcoran, G. C. Schild, and P. Minor (1997). Assessing the significance of reverse transcriptase activity in chick cell- derived vaccines. *Biologicals*, 25: 403-414.
- 28 - Schat AK and Sellers HS. (2008). Cell – culture methods. In: *A laboratory manual for isolation, identification and characterization of avian pathogens*. Fifth ed. pp:195 – 203.
- 29 - Smith, E. J. (1987). Endogenous avian leukemia viruses. In: *Avian Leukosis*. G.F. De Boer, ed. Martinus Nijhoff, Boston., 101-120.
- 30 - Smith, E.J., L. B. Crittenden, and J. Ignjatovic (1977). Comparative study of three methods for detecting leukosis viruses. *Infect. Immun.*, 16:500-504.
31. Smith, L.M., S. R. Brown, K. Hows, S. McLeod, S. S. Arshad, G. S. Barron, K. Venugopal, J. C. McKay, and L. N. Payne (1998). Development and application of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) tests for the detection of subgroup J avian leukosis virus. *Virus Res.*, 54:87-98.
- 32 - Tsang, S. X., W. M. Switzer, V. Shanmugam, J.A. Johnson, C. Goldsmith, A. Wright, A. Fadly, D. Thea, H. Jaffe, T.M. Folks, and W. Heneine (1999). Evidence of avian leukosis virus subgroup E and endogenous avian virus in measles and mumps vaccines derived from chicken cells: Investigation of transmission to vaccine recipients. *J Virol* .73:5843-5851.
- 33 - Weissmahr, R.N., J. Schupbach, and J. Boni (1997). Reverse transcriptase activity in chicken embryo fibroblast culture supernatants is associated with

particles containing endogenous avian retrovirus EAV- O RNA. J. Virol., 71:3005-3012.

34 - Zavala, G., and S. Cheng (2006). Detection and characterization of avian leukosis virus in Marek's disease vaccines. Avian Dis., 50:209-215.

35 - Zhao., X. Dong. and Z. Cui (2014). Isolation, identification, and characterization of a subgroup A avian leukosis virus from a contaminated live Newcastle Disease virus vaccine, first report in China. Poultry Science 93:2168-2174.

36 - Zhou, G., W. Cai, X. Liu, C. Niu, C. Gao, C.S. I., W. Zhang, L. Qu, and L. Han. (2011). A duplex real-time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction for the detection and quantitation of avian leukosis virus subgroups A and B. J Virol., Methods. 173:275-279.